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Interpersonal Intelligence: A Strengthening in Efforts to Improve Student Learning Achievement

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between interpersonal intelligence and student learning outcomes so that there is an increase and strengthening of student achievement. The method used in this research is field research with a correlational quantitative approach which aims to analyze the relationship between interpersonal intelligence and student achievement. The results of this study found that there is a significant relationship between interpersonal intelligence and student achievement. This can be proven from statistical calculations, namely r count is greater than r table ($0.995 > 0.347$) with a significant stage of 5%. Thus the alternative hypothesis (H_a) in this study is accepted and the hypothesis (H_0) in this study is rejected.

Keywords: Interpersonal Intelligence, Learning Achievement, Quantitative, Students

1. Introduction

Basically education in elementary school is an organized, planning, and continuous effort throughout life to foster students to become complete, adult, and cultured human beings. As a formal school education institution that is born and develops effectively and efficiently, it is a device that is obliged to provide services to the community in educating citizens. (Hasbullah et al., 2019). Education is also an activity to optimize the development of the potential, skills and personal characteristics of students. Educational activities are directed at achieving certain goals called educational goals (Aziizu, 2015). In Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning National education Article 1 Paragraph 1 states that education is a conscious and planned effort to create an atmosphere of learning and the learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual

strength, self-control, intelligence, noble character, and skills that are needed himself, society, nation and state (Visser-Wijnveen et al., 2014).

In the whole process of education in schools, learning activities are the most basic activities. This means that the success or failure of achieving educational goals depends a lot on how the learning process is experienced by students as learners (Kusumah et al., 2020).

Learning is one of the factors that influence and play an important role in shaping personal and individual behavior. Learning is an activity that can be done psychologically or physiologically (Rusman, 2011). Learning will produce changes in a person. To find out how far the changes have gone, it is necessary to assess them. Likewise with education, an assessment of the learning outcomes is always held. An assessment of the learning outcomes of a student to find out these learning objectives is known as learning achievement (Walid & Hadiwinarto, 2021).

Some people argue that high achievement can only be achieved by students who have high intelligence. In fact, students who have high intelligence do not necessarily get good achievement, because intelligence is not the only factor that determines student success, but there are several factors that influence it (Selviani, 2019).

Likewise for students to achieve high achievement in a learning process, not only using their intelligence abilities, but also relationships with other students which include interpersonal intelligence. Interpersonal intelligence is an individual's ability to interact with other people. Individuals who have high interpersonal intelligence tend to have excellent communication skills and the ability to empathize with other people (Nuryasin et al., 2016).

Interpersonal intelligence is the ability to understand and make differences in moods, intentions, motivations, and feelings towards others (Sujiono & Sujiono, 2010). Interpersonal intelligence is the intelligence to relate to other people, express and capture the mood, goals, motivation, and feelings of others (Sudarsana, 2018). Interpersonal intelligence allows us to be able to understand and communicate with others, see differences in mood, temperament, motivation and abilities (Oviyanti, 2017). This includes the ability to form and maintain relationships, and to know the various roles that exist in a group, both as a member and as a leader.

Students who have interpersonal intelligence like to interact with other people, both those of their age and those who are older or younger. With their ability to influence peers, they sometimes stand out very well in group work. Some students are very sensitive to the feelings of others, some of them can provide a variety of different perspectives on social problems and also help others (Campbell et al., 2006).

However, the reality in the field is not in accordance with the expected goals. There are still many students whose learning achievement does not meet the minimum completeness criteria. This is because most students do not use interpersonal intelligence in learning so that the learning process and the interaction process among their peers are not carried out well and effectively (Yani, 2017).

Based on the results of preliminary observations that students have interpersonal intelligence, but do not use interpersonal intelligence in carrying out learning activities, this can be seen when students who have difficulty in group work find it difficult to understand other people and it is difficult to build good relationships with other students at the time. the learning process so that there are some students whose learning achievement is not good, so the role of a teacher is very important to foster the intelligence of a student so that student achievement is what is expected. As we know, there are several factors that affect learning achievement, one of which is intelligence. The formulation of the problem in this study is to see whether there is a relationship between interpersonal intelligence and student achievement.

In previous research, it was stated that the better the interpersonal intelligence and learning motivation, the better the mathematics learning outcomes (Dewi et al., 2019), then the results of other studies state that. Kinesthetic intelligence has a relationship with learning outcomes, then interpersonal intelligence also has a relationship with student learning outcomes and intrapersonal intelligence also has a relationship with student learning outcomes

while kinesthetic, interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence are jointly confirmed to have a relationship with learning outcomes of students at Public Madrasah Tsanawiyah 1 Kota Bengkulu. therefore only four hypotheses Ha: what the authors propose is acceptable (Pendidikan et al., 2015)..

2. Method

This research method is field research with a correlational quantitative approach which aims to analyze the relationship between interpersonal intelligence and student achievement. Correlation research is a study that uses statistics in order to determine the relationship and level of the relationship between two or more variables (Privitera, 2016; Walker, 1989) Meanwhile, according to Arikunto (2014) correlational research is research conducted by research to determine the level of the relationship between two or more variables, without making changes, additions or manipulations to existing data. The population of this study were all students in 4th grade and 5th grade, amounting to 292 students. The sample taken is 10% of the total population. So that the sample taken is as many as 30 students who have good representation. This sampling technique used simple random sampling. because the sampling of members of the population is done randomly without considering the existing status in the population (Sugiyono, 2015).

This data collection technique uses a questionnaire that is distributed to the sample students. The questionnaire distributed is interpersonal intelligence data. Meanwhile, the learning achievement data were taken from the students' report cards. To strengthen the argument, interviews were conducted with selected students. The basis for the selection is students who stand out in terms of academic achievement at school (Sugiyono, 2015).

3. Results

The data were collected by distributing questionnaires to determine interpersonal intelligence and taking the average value of student report cards to determine student learning achievement which were then compiled and tabulated. Interpersonal intelligence questionnaires have been tested first on other students. So that the questionnaire is valid and reliable. Findings in the field can be seen in the following discussion.

Interpersonal Intelligence

Table 1: Interpersonal Intelligence Questionnaire Score Frequency

No	X	F	FX	X ²	F (X ²)
1	47	1	47	2209	2209
2	46	1	46	2116	2116
3	45	2	90	2025	4050
4	44	1	44	1936	1936
5	42	5	210	1764	8820
6	41	3	123	1681	5043
7	40	4	160	1600	6400
8	39	3	117	1521	4563
9	38	3	114	1444	4332
10	37	2	74	1369	2738
11	36	2	72	1296	2592
12	35	1	35	1225	1225
13	34	2	68	1156	2312
Amount		N=30	1200		48336

After tabulating and scoring the interpersonal intelligence questionnaire, the following results were obtained.

Table 2: TSR Category in Percentage of Variable X (Interpersonal Intelligence)

No	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	High	5	17%
2	Medium	20	66%
3	Low	5	17%
Amount		30	100%

From the table 2, it can be concluded that interpersonal intelligence is included in the medium category. This can be seen from the percentage table above, namely 20 samples (66%) are in the medium category.

Learning Achievement

To obtain data about student achievement, this is done by looking at the average grade of student report cards in odd semesters. Furthermore, the data were obtained and analyzed in a systematic way using statistical formulas.

Table 3: Odd Semester Report Card Score Frequency Score

No	Y	F	FY	Y ²	F (Y ²)
1	87	2	174	7569	15138
2	85	2	170	7225	14450
3	84	3	252	7056	21168
4	83	2	166	6889	13778
5	82	4	328	6724	26896
6	80	2	160	6400	12800
7	78	3	234	6084	18252
8	77	1	77	5929	5929
9	73	1	73	5329	5329
10	71	4	284	5041	20164
11	70	2	140	4900	9800
12	68	1	68	4624	4624
13	66	2	132	4356	8712
14	65	1	65	4225	4225
Amount		N=3 0	2323		18126 5

Based on the calculations in table 3, the student achievement scores are as follows:

Table 4: TSR Category In Percentage Variable Y (Learning Achievement)

No	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	High	7	23%
2	Medium	17	57%
3	Low	6	20%
Amount		30	100%

From the table 4, it can be concluded that learning achievement is in the medium category. This can be seen from the percentage table above, namely 17 samples (57%) are in the medium category.

The Relationship Between Interpersonal Intelligence And Student Achievement

To determine the relationship between interpersonal intelligence and student achievement, the product moment formula will be used, but first it is entered in the tabulation which is the score of the results of the interpersonal intelligence questionnaire and the value of student report cards.

Table 5: Data for Variable X and Variable Y obtained by Students

No	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
1	46	71	2116	5041	3266
2	34	80	1156	6400	2720
3	47	78	2209	6084	3666
4	42	70	1764	4900	2940
5	45	84	2025	7056	3780
6	42	82	1764	6724	3444
7	34	71	1156	5041	2414
8	39	71	1521	5041	2769
9	40	82	1600	6724	3280
10	41	82	1681	6724	3362
11	42	77	1764	5929	3234
12	39	78	1521	6084	3042
13	41	78	1681	6084	3198
14	40	83	1600	6889	3320
15	42	65	1764	4225	2730
16	42	84	1764	7056	3528
17	40	73	1600	5329	3280
18	35	84	1225	7056	2920
19	36	71	1296	5041	2556
20	39	87	1521	7569	3393
21	37	85	1369	7225	3145
22	36	87	1296	7569	3132
23	38	80	1444	6400	3040
24	40	83	1600	6889	3320
25	37	66	1369	4356	2442
26	45	68	2025	4624	3060
27	38	85	1444	7225	3230
28	44	82	1936	6724	3608
29	41	66	1681	4356	2706
30	38	70	1444	4900	2660
N=30	∑x =1200	∑y =233	∑x²=4836	∑y²=18125	∑xy =93185

After the data for variable X (Interpersonal Intelligence) and Variable Y (Learning Achievement) are tabulated, the next step is to manage the data according to the predetermined formula. The hypothesis to be tested in this study is whether there is a significant relationship between interpersonal intelligence and student achievement. Based on the data about Variable X (Interpersonal Intelligence) in the table above, it is processed using the product-moment formula, then the r_{xy} value is 0.995 then consulted with the criticism table on df. By looking at the "r" product moment table, it turns out that "df" is 28 at the 5% significant level of 0.374. The calculation result of r_{xy} (0.995) is greater than r table 5%, thus at the 5%

significant level there is a significant relationship so that the hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. This means that interpersonal intelligence is very influential on student achievement

4. Discussion

This research begins with research preparation, namely determining the place and time of research, after the place and time have been determined then preparing the research instruments to be used. In this study, the researchers distributed questionnaire questions to 30 students in the sample.

Research on interpersonal intelligence data is obtained using a questionnaire method or a questionnaire consisting of 20 question items with four alternative answers 4, 3, 2, 1. From the results of the calculation, the mean (average value) is 40, and the standard deviation is 3.34 The TSR which got a high score was 17% with 5 students, the moderate category was 66% with 20 students, while in the low category it was 17% with 5 students. This study aims to determine the relationship between interpersonal intelligence and student achievement. Interpersonal intelligence or it can also be called social intelligence, a person's ability and skills in creating relationships, building relationships and maintaining social relationships. So that both parties are in a situation of winning or strengthening each other. Interpersonal intelligence is the ability students have to express and capture the mood, goals, feelings, motivation, and feelings of others. While learning achievement is the result achieved by a student in his learning efforts as stated in his report card, through the learning achievement of a student can find out the progress he has achieved in learning.

Thus it can be concluded that students' interpersonal intelligence is included in the medium category, namely as many as 20 respondents (66%). This shows that almost all students have interpersonal intelligence. Student achievement data using the documentation technique of the results of the report card scores obtained the highest score of 87 and the lowest score of 65. From the calculation results obtained a mean value (average value) of 77 and a standard deviation of 6,800 then the TSR which got a high score of 23% with the number of students 7, the medium category is 57% with 17 students, while in the low category it is 20% with 6 students. Thus it can be concluded that the learning achievement of students is in the medium category (57%).

Results of the Analysis Regarding the Relationship between Interpersonal Intelligence and Learning Achievement

The results of this study indicate that the relationship between students' interpersonal intelligence has a significant effect on student achievement. By looking at the table of the product moment "r" value, it turns out that the df is 28 at the 5% significant level of 0.374. The result of the calculation of rxy (0.995) is greater than the 5% r table, which means that there is a significant influence between the variable interpersonal intelligence (X) and learning achievement (Y). Thus the alternative hypothesis (H_a) in this study is accepted and the hypothesis (H_o) in this study is rejected.

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